

Determination of Mercury in Foods and Water by Cold Vapour-Atomic Absorption Spectrometry

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The cold vapour-atomic absorption spectrometry is a selective procedure for the determination of mercury in samples of diverse origin¹. In view of the increased spread of pollutants and contaminants, the present communication reports the study of the interfering effects of complex matrices on the atomic absorption determination of mercury by the cold vapour technique.

Results and Discussion

The influence of bromide, bromate, iodide, iodate, periodate, sulphide, sulphite and thiosulphate on the determination of mercury was examined for acidic and alkali media. The depressing

effect of these inorganic species in acid medium is shown in Fig. 1. The severity of the decrease is in decreasing order : iodine compounds > sulphide > sulphite > thiosulphate > bromine compounds. These anions form stable compounds with mercury ions so that part of the latter cannot be reduced to mercury atoms which in turn cannot form the vapour of mercury. It is observed that the presence of increasing amounts of interfering species, increases the depressing effect without more inflections. Thus it appears that one compound is formed between mercury and any of the interfering species. It is evidenced that in the presence of Sn^{II} chloride solution, only one equilibrium is attained between

Fig. 1. Interference effects of anions on the determination of 15 ng/ml of mercury by the acid attack procedure (absorbance of 15 ng/ml of mercury was considered to be 100; all other results were related to this value): (1) iodide, iodate or periodate, (2) sulphide, (3) sulphite, (4) thiosulphate and (5) bromide or bromate. For the sake of clarity the plots in graphs (1) and (5) are given as mean results where the effect did not differ more than 5%, to show the general depression effect on the recovery of mercury.

mercury and the interfering species irrespective of its original oxidation state.

Experimental

A Perkin-Elmer 460 atomic absorption spectrometer was used with an electrically adapted Unicam HCL to suit the fitting of the instrument and a Perkin-Elmer mercury cold vapour analyser, having a 6 inch long absorption cell with quartz windows, and an air recirculation system. A three-way tap made ventilation possible between determination.

All reagents were of A.R. grade. Solutions were prepared in demineralised water.

Procedure: A mixture of the homogenised sample (5–10 g), demineralised water (20 ml), concentrated HNO_3 (3 ml) and concentrated HCl (3 ml) was heated gently on a steam-bath at 40–45° for 1 h. It was then cooled to ambient temperature and diluted to 50 ml with water.

Investigation in acidic medium: An aliquot (10 ml) of the supernatant solution of the above treated sample (or 100 ml of raw or tap water) was mixed with a solution containing distilled water (25 ml), 50% H_2SO_4 (5 ml) and 10% (w/v) Sn^{II} chloride (3 ml) solution. The reaction vessel was immediately closed and the recirculating operation started. After 2–3 min, the system reached equilibrium and the absorbance was displayed. The recirculating gas system was opened to purge the mercury vapour for 5 min.

Investigation in alkaline medium: An aliquot (10 ml) of the supernatant solution of the treated sample (or 100 ml of raw or tap water) was mixed with a solution containing distilled water (25 ml) and 50% H_2SO_4 (5 ml). It was cooled in ice-bath,

and then 6% (w/v) potassium permanganate solution added with constant stirring till the pink colour persisted for some while. It was left on a steam-bath for 2 h, cooled in an ice-bath, and then 7 M NaOH solution (30 ml) and 20% (w/v) hydroxylamine hydrochloride solution (2 ml) were added to reduce the excess of permanganate, followed by 10% (w/v) Sn^{II} chloride solution (3 ml). The procedure was otherwise identical with that for in acidic medium. The measurements of the standards and the samples were done at the same conditions.

The effect of the interfering anions disappears on changing the pH of the solution to the alkaline side. Fig. 2 shows that on making the analysing solution strongly alkaline by sodium hydroxide, the level the recovery of mercury approaches its original value.

Fig. 2. Effect of NaOH solution on the recovery of 15 ng/ml of mercury from different interfering anions: (1) recovery from NaOH without interfering anion, (2) in the presence of $5 \times 10^{-3} N$ sulphite ion, (3) $5 \times 10^{-4} N$ sulphide ion, (4) $2 \times 10^{-3} N$ thiosulphate ion, (5) $5 \times 10^{-1} N$ bromine or iodine compounds and (6) 0.5% of cyanox or ofunack.

The effect of insecticides on the absorbance signal of mercury was also examined for acidic and alkaline media. The following insecticides dissolved in acid solution (up to 0.5% w/v or v/v) do not interfere: endrin, bayfolan, wuxal, landrin, lannate, gardona, irral, stimufol, larvin, cybolt and danitol. On the contrary, ofunack or cyanox decreases the mercury absorbance signal by ca. 65%. These two insecticides contain in their chemical structures the weak $\text{P}=\text{S}$ bond which is easily reduced by Sn^{II} chloride to give most probably the sulphide ion which acts upon mercury ions to prevent them from forming the atomic vapour. However, when the analysis solution containing ofunack or cyanox is made strongly alkaline, the depressive interference of ofunack or cyanox is removed.

The detection limit for mercury determination in the presence of such concomitants is 1 ng/g, and the relative standard deviation is ca. 2.38%.

TABLE 1—COMPARISON OF ACID REDUCTION AND ACID ATTACK-ALKALI REDUCTION PROCEDURES FOR DETERMINATION OF MERCURY IN DIFFERENT SAMPLES AND TOLERANCE LIMITS OF THE CONVENTIONAL STANDARD SPECIFICATIONS

Sample	Concn. of Hg (ng/g) Reduction medium			Tolerance limit**
	Acid	Alkali	% RSD*	
Tap water	0.84	2.40	4.25	1.0
Raw Nile water	1.61	4.61	2.30	0.98 - 1.03
(Embaba industrial province)				
Processed animal feeds	1.25	2.59	3.60	2 - 36
Canned beef	1.15	4.10	1.84	0.8 - 150
Processed cheese	2.30	3.11	1.00	0.6 - 8
Canned fishes	0.93	4.21	1.30	1.6 - 180

*For 9 replicates carried out at different time intervals.

**Ref. 4.

The proposed acid attack-alkali reduction procedure was applied to determine mercury in samples of different origin. Table 1 summarises a comparison between the results of application of the two

procedures. The results of application of acid attack-alkali reduction procedure are in good agreement concerning the precision of the data.

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